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10 **Economic performance and risk of farming systems specialized in perennial**
11 **crops: an analysis of Italian hazelnut production**

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25 **Economic performance and risk of farming systems specialized in** 26 **perennial crops: an analysis of Italian hazelnut production**

27

28 **1. Introduction**

29 In economic terms farm resilience relates to the capacity of a farm business to survive various risks
30 and shocks (Lien et al., 2007). This implies that the combined assessment of economic performance
31 and risks are key in determining the resilience and sustainability of farming systems (Meuwissen et
32 al., 2018; Reidsma et al., 2015). Assessing farm risk is particularly important when farms are
33 specialized in producing perennial crops, where changing production patterns are seriously
34 constrained by high costs and lengthy implementation time. Under these conditions, risk should be
35 carefully managed by using available risk management strategies and tools. In recognizing this
36 problem, agricultural policies have focused on supporting farmers to improve their management of
37 farm-related risk. For example, the European Union's (EU) Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)
38 provides three different risk management measures, based on public-private partnerships within the
39 framework of the EU Rural Development Policy (RDP)¹ (Bardají and Garrido, 2016). These are: farm
40 insurance premium subsidies, mutual funds and the Income Stabilization Tool (IST). The latter is
41 aimed at levelling out the variability in farm income over the years and to account for price risk, even
42 if this tool has not yet been implemented throughout the EU (Severini et al., 2018; Trestini et al., 2017
43 and 2018).

44 Assessing overall risk, as well as identifying and quantifying the type of risk facing a farming system
45 (including the risk related to yield, product price and quality) is a preliminary requirement in deciding
46 which strategy and tools are more suited to individual circumstances. Indeed, farmers are affected by
47 several different types of risk: there exist production risk and market risks (Hardaker et al., 2015),
48 with the former principally being caused by a sudden and unexpected drop in product prices. Risk

¹ Regulation (EU) No. 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 December 2013 (OJ L347, 20.12.2013, p.487).

49 management should, therefore, be tailored to coping with the most important risks and by selecting
50 the most appropriate strategies and tools from those available. The latter are often suitable for
51 managing only the risk arising from one of the aforementioned variables: for example, farm
52 insurance² can be used to manage yield risks while future contracts can control price risk.

53 Production risk is not only related to the amount of production but also to its quality. Negative climatic
54 conditions and pests can have detrimental implications for the quality of the product which, in turn,
55 might cause the price paid to farmers to decline below the expected level. Finally, the level and
56 sources of risk, as well as farm profitability, can be expected to differ between different production
57 areas, even when considering the same crop. Hence, it is important to explore these issues in different
58 production areas and compare the results obtained to provide information which is specifically
59 tailored to the producers operating in those areas.

60 The analysis outlined in this paper will focus on hazelnut production in Italy. Confirming Cristofori
61 et al. (2008), interest in this crop has been increasing due to the growing demand from the processing
62 industry (chocolate, confectionery and bakery products) (Dobhal et al., 2018; Liso et al., 2017;
63 Cristofori et al., 2015). As tree-bearing nuts, the hazelnut (*Corylus avellana* L.) predominates in Italy
64 (CREA, 2018). With its average annual production of nearly 106,000 tons of hazelnuts (in shell) for
65 the 2007-2016 period, Italy is the second largest producer in the world (14.3%) after Turkey, which
66 has always dominated the world market (in the same period, nearly 558,500 tons on average were
67 produced, 75.0% of the world's hazelnut production) (FAOstat, 2018). Moreover, Italy plays a central
68 role on the international market: if, on the one hand it is one of the main buyers of Turkish hazelnuts,
69 on the other hand, it also re-exports part of this import as semi-finished products (Liso et al., 2017).

² The current National Rural Development Programme of Italy supports crop insurance which covers only combinations of negative events and not single-peril insurance (generally hail) (European Commission, 2019). Events are classified as *catastrophic weather risks* and other *weather-related risks*. The former are not very common but they do have a significant impact on crop production; they include flood, drought and frost. The latter are more frequent and include, for example, excessive snow, excessive rain, hail and high winds. Crop insurance contracts can include approximately five different combinations of events. In the hazelnut sector a contract covering all catastrophic weather risks and hail has been made available to farmers in recent years. This has been channelled through various producers' organizations, which provide technical assistance to farmer members.

70 Italian hazelnut production is highly geographically concentrated and specialized due to its
71 environmental and climatic conditions, the technical knowledge and human skills developed over
72 time, and the expert selection of high-quality varieties (Piacentini et al., 2015). Approximately 90%
73 of the Italian harvest is destined for the processing industry (USDA, 2014), which increasingly
74 demands high-quality products (Cristofori et al., 2008). Accordingly, farmers receive a price for their
75 produce and this is markedly influenced by quality parameters, such as: the size of the shelled nut,
76 the ratio of without/with shell nut weights, the quantity of defective nuts and the type of defect.

77 Several studies concerning profitability have been conducted on different crop systems with the aim
78 of evaluating alternative production systems in vegetables (Halloran et al., 2005), small grains (Kolb
79 et al., 2010 and 2012), corn-soybean rotations (Cox et al., 1999; Davis et al., 2012; Caldwell et al.,
80 2014) and perennial crops, like apples and cherries (Seavert et al., 2006). These studies have often
81 utilized farm budgets to compare profitability but they did not explicitly analyze the risk of farming
82 activities.

83 Risk analysis may also be used to identify systems with a degree of uncertain profitability (Brown et
84 al., 2018). Several studies have been developed to analyze the risks faced by various farming systems.
85 For example, Monjardino et al. (2013) have studied net return functions in order to observe the risk
86 of low-rainfall cropping systems, in which farmers applied low rates of nitrogen. Osaki and Batalha
87 (2014) have tested an optimization model of production factors to maximize the gross contribution
88 margin in grain farms at risk. Luo et al. (2017) have examined the risk of gross margin (GM)
89 variability, which was linked to the adaptation to climate change in the Australian cotton industry.

90 Anton and Kimura (2009) have separated the roles of yield, price and costs in determining the final
91 variability in the farm results of different field crops in different regions of Germany. This is an
92 important suggestion for stakeholders to focus on the most important factors determining income risk.

93 The authors of this paper know of no study to date which has analyzed profitability and risk relating
94 to hazelnut production. However, there exists an extensive body of literature relating to Turkish
95 hazelnut production, specifically: sustainability (Castro and Swart, 2017), economic efficiency (Kilik

96 et al., 2009), the impacts of a policy change (Bayramoglu et al., 2010; Sisman, 2016), risk attitudes
97 to organic and conventional producers (Demiryürek et al., 2012) and the profit level (Fidan and
98 Sahinli, 2010).

99 Several methods have been proposed for identifying and quantifying risk in economic studies (Goetz,
100 1993, Gocsik et al., 2013; Hermann et al., 2014; Groen et al., 2014). Stochastic simulation is usually
101 applied to study the impact of risk on a farm business (Antle, 1983). Of these, the most commonly
102 used is the Monte Carlo (MC) simulation (Castañeda-Vera and Garrido, 2017; Kamali et al., 2017;
103 Lien et al., 2007; Luo et al., 2017; Fariña et al. 2013; Monjardino et al., 2013; Ghasemi et al., 2012).
104 This numerical, parametric technique combines information regarding the distribution of different
105 stochastic input variables. By running multiple iterations, it can provide an insight into the range of
106 possible outcomes and the likelihood or probability of these outcomes. Less used in the field of
107 agricultural research is the use of MC to demonstrate the sensitivity of the outcomes to input variables
108 (Ghasemi et al., 2012). In comparison with other applications (Lien et al., 2007), the analysis
109 presented in this paper will focus on a single crop, instead of a whole-farm model. This is due to the
110 fact that hazelnuts are often produced in specialized orchards in Italy; in some regions (e.g.
111 Campania), farms may grow hazelnuts together with walnut, chestnuts and other crops.

112 Based on historical farm-level data, the aim of this study was to assess and compare the level and the
113 risk of the profitability of hazelnut in the main areas of production in Italy. Stepwise regression
114 analysis was also been used to combine the distribution of the most important variables affecting the
115 profitability of the crop: yield, product quality and price. This enabled the quantification of the
116 relative importance of these stochastic variables on the risk of hazelnut production. The specific
117 objectives of the analysis were: (i) to assess the degree of profitability and risk in the main areas of
118 production; (ii) to test whether profitability and risk differed among areas; (iii) to identify the key
119 parameters making the greatest contribution to the risk involved with farm activities; (iv) and to verify
120 whether there were differences in risk-generating parameters among the four regions.

121 It is expected that the results of this analysis will support farmers in the different production areas: in
122 deciding whether it is worth changing their risk management strategies; in identifying the most
123 relevant risk sources; and in selecting the most appropriate risk management tools. Furthermore, these
124 results could also be useful in assessing whether there is potential for developing innovative risk
125 management tools to mitigate risks for which tools are not currently available. Opportunities offered
126 by the CAP could be put to work in this endeavour.

127 The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 will describe the study area, data and methods used;
128 Section 3 will present the results of the analysis; and, lastly, Section 4 - the Discussion and Conclusion
129 - will close the paper.

130

131 **2. Material and methods**

132 *2.1. Study area*

133 The key hazelnut production areas in Italy are located almost exclusively within four regions: for the
134 period 2008-2017, Campania and Lazio jointly accounted for approximately two thirds of national
135 production (34% and 33% respectively), with the remaining production located in Piedmont (20%),
136 Sicily (11%), and other regions (2%) (Istat, 2017) (Fig. 1).

137

138 Fig. 1: Study locations map - Main hazelnut production regions in Italy.

139 Hazelnut production in these four regions plays a crucial role in the local economy as well as an
 140 environmental safeguard (Anania and Aiello, 1999). The relevance of these areas is linked to the
 141 geographical spread of hazelnut production and the phenomenon of socio-economic development,
 142 which integrates technology, commerce and social relations (Franco et al., 2014, Piacentini et al.,
 143 2015). Furthermore, the spatial polarization of hazelnut production is the key element to boosting the
 144 local production system towards becoming a specialized agro-industrial district (Franco et al., 2014).
 145 There is a growing interest in organic hazelnut production (Pancino and Franco, 2009); it represented
 146 a very small share of production in Italy until 2013 after which the surface area of land dedicated to
 147 organic hazelnut production increased (FADNdatabase). Due to the lack of a long enough time series,
 148 it was not possible to include an analysis relating to organic hazelnut production. However, according
 149 to Franco and Pancino (2009), the gross margins of organic hazelnut management can be higher or
 150 lower than that of conventional hazelnut management, in accordance with the intensity of the

151 cropping technique. It is not, therefore, possible to conclude that there is a significant difference
152 between these management forms. This study will, therefore, present a joint analysis.

153 Albeit with a degree of fluctuation, Italian hazelnut production has grown constantly during the period
154 2008-2017. This increase originated from the Piedmont and Lazio regions, both of which more than
155 compensated for the declining production in Sicily (Istat, 2017). Whilst the four regions (Piedmont,
156 Lazio, Sicily and Campania) under consideration possess ideal soil and climate conditions for
157 hazelnut production (growing the local cultivars), crop production at the farm level is affected by
158 variability over time due to climatic factors and pests (Piacentini et al., 2015). The yield data show a
159 slight increase in Piedmont, Lazio and Campania and a slight reduction in Sicily for the period 2008-
160 2017 (Fig. 2); this has resulted in slow growth at the national level.

161
162 Fig. 2: Development of hazelnut yields in the main four Italian regions (tons/ha) – year 2008-2017.
163 Source: Istat 2017.

164 Average yields levels differ among the four aforementioned regions: they are higher than the national
165 average (1.59 tons/ha) in Lazio and Campania (1.95 and 1.86 tons/ha respectively), lower in Piedmont
166 and even lower in Sicily (Istat, 2017).

167
168 *2.2. Data*

169 The data used in this study was obtained from the Italian Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN)
170 sample and it refers to the period 2008-2016 (CREA, 2018). An original sample of 1,756 observations

171 (obs.) was extracted and then filtered in order to account for two factors. First, observations referring
 172 to the installation period of the crop were excluded because, for the first 6 years after plantation, there
 173 is no production or it is negligible (Frascarelli, 2017). 129 observations were, therefore, excluded.
 174 Second, only observations of farms with at least 1 hectare (ha) under hazelnut production were taken
 175 into account to avoid the inclusion of hazelnuts, which had not been grown for commercial purposes;
 176 consequently, additional 435 observations were excluded. These steps resulted in a final sample of
 177 1,192 observations regarding Piedmont, Lazio, Sicily and Campania (Table 1).

178 Table 1
 179 Sample size by region and year.

Regions	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	Obs. (2008-2016)
Piedmont	62	73	73	64	68	67	75	72	55	609
Lazio	13	16	29	39	45	52	99	30	40	363
Campania	13	15	23	22	14	15	19	26	28	175
Sicily	3	4	5	6	4	5	7	6	5	45
TOTAL	91	108	130	131	131	139	200	134	128	1,192

180 Source: Authors' elaborations on Italian FADN data.

181 The sample size would appear to be sufficiently large for performing the analysis by region even if
 182 the results for Sicily should be considered with caution due to the relatively small sample size. The
 183 key variables of interest are: crop gross margin (GM), yield, product quality and the standard- quality
 184 price of hazelnuts without shells, as well as specific variable costs. All values refer to a single hectare
 185 of land to make comparable observations and production areas. Monetary values were deflated using
 186 annual coefficients (Istat, 2018) to permit comparability over time.

187

188 2.3. Profitability and variability analysis

189 Profitability was assessed by using the crop GM (€/ha), that is, the difference between crop revenues
 190 and the specific variable crop costs of farms (Castaneda-Vera and Garrido, 2017; Luo et al., 2017):

191

$$192 \text{GM}_{i,t} = R_{i,t} - Cv_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

193

194 where GM is the unitary gross margin, R are revenues and C_v are specific variable costs associated
195 to the crop in the i -th farm in the t -th year.

196 Although different profitability indexes could also have been used to account for general and fixed
197 costs, the GM was preferred because farms can differ markedly in terms of the source of production
198 factors, such as labour and machinery. Some farms rely totally on family (often unpaid) labour and
199 purchased machinery while others make great use of hired labour and rented machinery. Thus, GM
200 seems to be the most suitable index with which to compare crop profitability.

201 The probability density functions (PDFs) of GM, as well as yield, price and quality index, were
202 described by using four moments, including mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), skewness and kurtosis.
203 The centre of the distribution (μ) was used to compare the profitability among the different areas.
204 Variability was evaluated in absolute (σ) and relative terms, with respect to the mean values
205 (Coefficient of Variation, CV), in observing potential outcomes.

206 To enhance the role played by the non-symmetric nature of the distributions, the degree of skewness
207 and kurtosis were observed to reveal insights regarding the probability of negative results and extreme
208 events respectively.

209

210 *2.4. Risk analysis*

211 All the farms in this study in each of the four regions were assumed to face the same risk. The
212 available data do not permit a single-farm analysis due to the relatively limited number of farms
213 which were observed for more than three years. However, each region is relatively small in surface
214 area and homogeneous regarding climatic and soil characteristics. Therefore, the assumption of an
215 analysis of single farms per region seems reasonable. Economic results are strongly affected by the
216 development of product prices. However, all farms in all regions operate in the same market (that is,
217 the international market) and they, therefore, face the same price risk.

218 The risk associated with producing the hazelnut crop was assessed by calculating several risk indexes,
219 starting from the PDF of the unitary GM. As stated in Luo et al. (2017), the CV is a simplified measure

220 of risk because it measures the width or spread of a distribution. The riskier condition has a wider
221 range of potential outcomes, thus wider distributions are associated with greater risk. However, the
222 standard deviation or other measures of spread dispersion around the distribution mean are insufficient
223 measures of risk when used alone (Kandulu et al., 2012; Monjardino et al., 2013). Therefore,
224 economic risk measures were presented as a combination of different indicators to quantify the
225 expected GM at different confidence levels for each area.

226 In order to obtain information on the left side of the distributions, a semi-standard deviation³ (SSD)
227 and a semi-coefficient of variation (SCV) were also computed and analysed (Mun, 2006; Monjardino
228 et al., 2013) - because they specifically focus on the downside risk exposure. Commonly used risk
229 measures were also used: the break-even point ($P[GM] \geq 0$, i.e. the probability of returning a profit),
230 the Value at Risk (VaR) and Expected Tail Loss (ETL). According to Dowd (2007), VaR is the
231 maximum loss which may be expected over a given horizon period at a given confidence level. It was
232 calculated as follows:

233

$$234 \quad VaR = E(GM) - V^* \quad (2)$$

235

236 where $E(GM)$ is the expected mean of GM and V^* is the expected value of GM at a confidence level
237 of 95%. That is, how much of the expected GM could be lost if a tail event (i.e. negative but unlikely)
238 occurs. The VaR is contingent on the choice of confidence level: it will generally change when the
239 confidence level changes. VaR only states the maximum loss if a tail event (i.e. exceeding 95% c.l.)
240 does not occur. It refers to a chosen probability level (e.g., 95%) but reveals nothing about that which
241 could be lost after that level (i.e. the remaining 5% of cases). However, if a tail event occurs, it can
242 be expected to lose more than the VaR; the VaR figure itself gives no indication of how much that
243 might be (Dowd, 2007). To overcome this drawback, the ETL index was also calculated; this refers

³ The semi-standard deviation was calculated using the *RiskSemiStdDev* function in @Risk. This is the standard deviation of the values in the distribution below the mean.

244 to the expected value of losses if extreme events occur. The latter are defined as those in which the
245 losses (L) exceed the VaR (Dowd, 2007):

246

$$247 \quad ETL = E[L|L > VaR] \quad (3)$$

248

249 ETL was calculated using the approach proposed by Dowd (2007). This consists of: slicing the left-
250 tail into 10 slices, each of which has the same probability mass (95.0%, 95.5%, 96.0%, until 99.5%);
251 estimating the VaR associated with each slice; and taking the ETL as the average of these VaRs. The
252 results of VaR and *ETL* were also compared with the values of expected GM at 95% c.l. ($E[GM]^{95\%}$)
253 and an average of the expected GMs in the last 5% of c.l. on the left tail of the curve ($E[GM]^{>95\%}$)
254 respectively. VaR and ETL can also be expressed as relative values (VaR% and ETL%) (i.e. using
255 the average GM as a denominator).

256

257 *2.5. Monte Carlo analysis*

258 Similar to the work by Luo et al. (2017), an MC analysis was performed. The MC sampling
259 framework (Hardaker et al., 2015) was used to iteratively draw hazelnut yields, prices and quality
260 indicators from the PDF, to model input data and to simulate their impact on GM. Accounting for the
261 stochastic nature of the GM, it is possible to consider GM as:

262

$$263 \quad \widetilde{GM}_{i,t} = \widetilde{R}_{i,t} - Cv_i \quad (4)$$

264

265 where the tildes identify what is assumed to be a stochastic variable. $\widetilde{R}_{i,t}$ is derived through the
266 product of simulated crop yields (\widetilde{y}), price of hazelnut without shell (\widetilde{p}) and a quality index (\widetilde{q}):

267

$$268 \quad \widetilde{R}_{i,t} = \widetilde{y}_{i,t} \cdot \widetilde{p}_t \cdot \widetilde{q}_{i,t} \quad (5)$$

269

270 Yields were calculated as the ratio of produced quantity to cultivated area in each farm (i) in every
271 year (t). The FADN does not provide price data but only the total value of production. By dividing
272 this figure by the produced quantity, it is possible to identify a proxy of the average received price.
273 The level of this indicator is strongly affected by two main factors: the development of market price
274 (i.e. expressed in terms of standard-quality hazelnuts without shells) and the average quality of the
275 product obtained on the farm. The average annual market prices were obtained from the Chamber of
276 Commerce, Industry, Crafts, and Agriculture (CCICA). The price series relating to the Viterbo
277 CCICA and Avellino CCICA were used for the Piedmont-Lazio and Campania-Sicily areas
278 respectively, after they had been deflated. A positive price trend was observed during the analysis
279 due to the relatively high prices observed in the 2014-2016 period (Fig. 3). Price levels did not differ
280 very much in the two markets, Viterbo and Avellino respectively. The two series were highly
281 correlated with a peak in 2015 in both series.

282

283

284 Fig. 3: The development in the deflated price of hazelnuts (without shells) in Viterbo and Avellino (€/kg) – Years 2008 -
285 2016.

286 Source: CCICA of Viterbo and Avellino.

287

288 The presence of such a positive trend could lead to incorrect estimates of the price risk, which is faced
289 by farmers. Assessing the spread around the mean of the series in these circumstances overestimates
290 the price risk faced by farmers, for which the ignoring of such a trend cannot be assumed. As is

291 standard practice in the literature relating to risk analysis, the price series has been detrended to only
292 assess the spread around the estimated trend in order to refer to uncertain developments in price
293 (Miranda and Glauber, 1997; Lien et al., 2007).

294 The resulting prices were applied to each farm located in a region, assuming that all farms within a
295 region faced the same price in a given year. Inter-farm price heterogeneity was used as a proxy for
296 product quality index. Indeed, farmers sell products in shell which are heterogeneous in quality, a fact
297 which depends on two main parameters: the technical conversion rate from product in shell to product
298 without shell (usually approximately 45%), and the technical characteristics of the product. The latter
299 refer to the relative occurrence of empty (due to hazelnut weevil), aborted nuts (due to bugs) and
300 kernels which have been damaged by insects, causing an unpleasant taste and odour, both of which
301 render the nuts unsuitable for processing production. These technical parameters strongly affect the
302 net price obtained, and they could vary over time, according to climatic conditions and farm specific
303 management practices. In order to account for quality-related aspects, an overall and concise quality
304 index was calculated as follows:

305

$$306 \quad \tilde{q}_{i,t} = (\tilde{P}_{i,t}/\tilde{p}_t) \quad (6)$$

307

308 where P is the average revenue obtained for each produced quantity of hazelnut in shell. This was
309 obtained as the ratio between total gross production value (TGP) to produced quantity (Q), using
310 FADN data from each farm and for each year:

311

$$312 \quad P_{i,t} = (TGP/Q)_{i,t} \quad (7)$$

313

314 The quality index (6) is low when the product quality is low and *vice versa* so that it positively
315 correlates with the crop GM.

316 As stated by Fariña et al. (2013), all crop specific costs (including direct costs, reuses and other costs),
 317 as reported in the FADN database, were not considered as stochastic, using the average variable cost
 318 for each region. This seems a reasonable assumption given that most of these costs are planned and
 319 incurred in the early stages of crop activity; therefore, the degree of uncertainty related to costs is
 320 low.

321 The stochastic MC simulations, developed using the Version 7.5.2 @Risk™ software (Palisade
 322 Corporation, Newfield, New York)⁴, are described as in Figure 4.

323

324

325 Fig. 4. Diagram of the MC simulations.

326

327 The random components, referring to hazelnut yields, price and quality are the key input variables
 328 which were used in the simulation to produce a PDF for GM. This reflects the uncertainty of farm
 329 business profitability (the key output variable) for the four production areas under consideration.
 330 Combining a very large number of different possible input parameters, 10,000 random iterations were
 331 used to define the simulated range of farm business profitability. Correlations between the three key
 332 input variables were verified by using Spearman Rank correlation coefficients. If significant, such

⁴ Available at: <https://www.palisade.com/risk/default.asp>

333 correlation coefficients would be considered in the MC simulations, using the related software
334 features.

335

336 2.6. Probability distributions functions of key variables

337 The PDFs for yield, price and quality index were fitted considering a range of suitable PDFs,
338 including Normal, Weibull, InvGauss, Logistic, Pearson5, Uniform and Beta distributions. These
339 distributions were ranked according to the goodness-of-fit tests, which provides a measure of how
340 closely the fitted distribution matched the data distribution. Unlike Monjardino et al. 2013, who used
341 the Anderson-Darling statistics test to observe cereal yields variability, the Akaike Information
342 Criteria (AIC) statistics test was chosen to measure the goodness-of-fit of each input variable in this
343 paper. This criterion defines the best density function from the log-likelihood function, taking into
344 account the number of parameters of the fitted distribution. It is based on the following expression:

345

$$346 \quad AIC = 2k - 2 \ln L \quad (8)$$

347

348 where L is the likelihood function and k is the number of parameters estimated for the fit. This test
349 was chosen because its informative prior distributions and hierarchical structures tend to reduce the
350 amount of overfitting, compared to what would happen under simple least squares or maximum
351 likelihood estimation (Gelman et al, 2014; Burnham and Anderson, 2004; Bozdogan, 1987).

352 The PDFs of the key input variables were selected, using the *BestFit* in @Risk software, and they
353 were compared with the fits from all distributions, for which valid fits were generated. The selected
354 PDFs were used in the MC simulation of GM. Hazelnut prices were found to be logistically
355 distributed, as in the case of wheat by Monjardino et al. (2013), being the PDFs typified by
356 *leptocurticity* and positive skewness. Different fits were observed for yields and quality index
357 distribution data, as shown in Tables 2 and 3.

358 Table. 2

Hazelnut yield distribution parameters in the risk model.Regions	Probability distribution function	Min.	Max.	μ	Median	σ	Skewness	Kurtosis
Piedmont	Normal	0.000	59.962	19.264	19.286	9.037	0.199	3.520
Lazio	Logistic	0.000	48.193	21.150	21.560	8.665	0.203	3.794
Campania	Weibull	3.871	60.000	23.011	23.316	10.389	0.705	3.792
Sicily	Extvalue	0.661	32.000	14.557	15.000	7.356	0.504	3.055

359 Source: Authors' elaborations on Italian FADN data.

360

361 Table 3.

Hazelnut quality index distribution parameters in the risk model.Region s	Probability distribution function	Min.	Max.	μ	Median	σ	Skewness	Kurtosis
Piedmont	BetaGeneral	0.000	0.798	0.450	0.420	0.176	-0.106	2.718
Lazio	Gamma	0.113	0.974	0.500	0.471	0.164	0.381	2.717
Campania	Extvalue	0.193	0.963	0.522	0.483	0.159	0.480	2.760
Sicily	Extvalue	0.100	0.757	0.370	0.352	0.127	0.757	4.012

362 Source: Authors' elaborations on Italian FADN data.

363

364 The distributions of the key input variables were observed with the aim of deleting outliers, which
365 would have biased the simulation. In particular, observations reporting yields higher than 6 tons/ha
366 and a quality index higher than 0.8 were eliminated. The latter was performed by using the
367 *RiskTruncate* functions during the simulation. Boundaries were chosen on the basis of collected data
368 and interviews with experts in hazelnut production.

369 In order to verify whether the distributions of the variables under consideration (yield, price, quality
370 index and GM) were significantly different among the regions, the Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney test
371 was applied given the results of the Shapiro test⁵ (Wilcoxon, 1945; Mann and Whitney, 1947; Fay
372 and Proschan, 2010) (Table A1 in the Appendix). Being nonparametric in nature, this test does not
373 require normally distributed data. The Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test compares two treatments (e.g.
374 the yield distribution for variables relating to two regions), using scores (ranks) which replace

⁵ The results of the Shapiro test permit the rejection of the hypothesis of normality of the distribution in all but one case. Such tests were carried out by using the Rstudio software (Crawley, 2012).

375 numerical data in order to validate or not the statistical hypothesis that the samples are not
376 significantly different (Wilcoxon, 1945).

377

378 *2.7. Sensitivity analysis*

379 A sensitivity analysis was performed to identify those input variables which impact GM outcomes
380 and the degree of this impact. First, a multivariate regression between GM and the key input variables
381 was estimated (Saltelli et al., 2008). Subsequently, following Ghasemi et al. (2012) and Kamali et al.
382 (2017), a multivariate stepwise regression analysis was performed. It consisted of varying the level
383 of one input parameter across the possible range while other input parameters were kept constant at
384 their mean values. This provided a quantification of the effect of each factor on the dependent variable
385 of interest. The dependent variable used in the model was the GM output, and the independent
386 variables were each a random function, defined for each stochastic input variable of the model (i.e.
387 yield, price and quality index).

388 Since the variables are measured in different units of measurement, a Regression-Mapped Values
389 approach was used. These mapped values are the beta coefficients produced from a regression which
390 uses standardized variables (Kamali, 2017; Ghasemi, 2012). The results of this approach are shown
391 by means of tornado graphs. The length of the bar shows the change in output due to a unitary standard
392 deviation change in the input.

393

394 **3. Results**

395 *3.1. Expected profitability*

396 In order to assess the profitability in hazelnut production, the average unitary GM (€/ha) was
397 considered. Campania and Lazio were the most profitable regions for hazelnut production with the
398 Piedmont region attaining third position with the region of Sicily trailing significantly (Table 4).

399 Table 4.

400 Descriptive statistics of the gross margin.

Regions	GM PDF	μ (€/ha)	σ (€/ha)	CV (%)	SSD (€/ha)	SCV (%)	Skewness	Kurtosis
---------	--------	--------------	-----------------	--------	------------	---------	----------	----------

Piedmont	Log-Logistic	4,754	3,009	63	1,787	38	1.54	9.71
Lazio	Log-Logistic	5,032	2,760	55	1,764	35	0.88	6.02
Campania	Pearson5	5,690	3,047	54	1,705	30	1.75	9.23
Sicily	Weibull	2,786	1,816	65	1,108	40	0.94	4.00

401 Source: Authors' elaborations on Italian FADN data.
402

403 Although Campania is the most profitable region (5,690 €/ha), followed by Lazio (5,032 €/ha), the
404 Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test revealed that the difference between these two regions is not
405 statistically significant (see the Appendix). The low profitability of Sicily is due to the specific
406 structural characteristics of Sicilian farms, which are often located in mountain areas with steep slopes
407 and limited field size, thereby minimising the use of machinery.

408

409 3.2. Economic-risk performance

410 As suggested by the width dispersion of the GM level around the mean (i.e. large levels of CV) (Table
411 4), hazelnut production was found to be quite risky. However, differences exist between regions: it is
412 higher in Piedmont and Sicily than in the other regions. The GM distributions in the four regions are
413 not symmetric (Fig. 5).

414 Fig. 5. Probability density functions of the unitary GM of hazelnut (€/ha).

415 Source: Authors' elaborations on Italian FADN data.

416

417 Hence it is important to focus on the left-side tails of the distributions (i.e. the worst outcomes). The
 418 SSD and the SCV confirm that Campania is exposed to a lower risk than is the case with the other
 419 regions.

420 The PDFs of GM are positive or right skewed for all four regions and this is particularly the case with
 421 Piedmont and Campania. Contemporaneously, a high kurtosis provides information regarding the
 422 probabilities of extreme and catastrophic events (potential large losses) and these are relatively higher
 423 in Piedmont and Campania. Here skewness values are higher than 1, demonstrating that these regions
 424 face a high frequency of low GM levels. Further insights can be obtained by observing the VaR and
 425 ETL, both of which are also specifically focused on the left tail of the PDFs. The VaR study was
 426 performed by comparing the absolute and relative terms of VaR with the value of the expected GM
 427 at a confidence level of 95% (Table 5).

428 Table 5.

Economic risk measures. Regions	μ (€/ha)	Value at Risk			Expected Tail Loss			Probability of Break-even
		$E[GM]^{95\%*}$	VaR (€)	$VaR\%$ *	ETL (€)	$ETL\%*$	$E[GM]^{>95\%*}$	$P[GM] \geq 0$
Piedmont	4,754	767	3,987	83.86	4,691	98.7	63	97.8%
Lazio	5,032	1,025	4,007	79.64	4,854	96.5	178	98.0%
Campania	5,690	2,099	3,591	63.11	3,981	69.9	171	100.0%
Sicily	2,786	429	2,358	84.61	2,531	90.8	255	99.7%

429 * - $E[GM]^{95\%}$ measures the expected GM at a c.l. of 95%;

430 - $VaR\%$ is a relative measure of VaR, referring to the mean;

431 - $E[GM]^{>95\%}$ measures an average of the expected GMs in the last 5% of c.l. on the left tail of the curve;

432 - $ETL\%$ is a relative measure of ETL referring to the mean.

433 Source: Authors' elaborations on Italian FADN data.

434

435 Despite the highest absolute values of VaR being recorded in Piedmont and Lazio, $VaR\%$ suggested
 436 that the highest relative risk was to be located in Sicily and Piedmont. Indeed, the $VaR\%$ was lower
 437 in Campania where, at the 95% confidence level, farmers could lose 63% of the regional average
 438 GM. Even if this were to happen, farmers would still gain € 2,099/ha ($E[GM]^{95\%}$), that is, the highest
 439 expected value at that confidence level of the four regions. The $VaR\%$ index was also high in Lazio
 440 but less than in Piedmont and Sicily. All these results imply that Sicily is the riskiest region for
 441 hazelnut production, followed by Piedmont and Lazio, and finally Campania.

442 The risk profile for each region was further defined by an interpretation of the $P[GM] \geq 0$: the
443 probability of breaking even was greater than 90% for all regions under investigation. Moreover, it
444 seems important to analyse the possible economic results which may occur if catastrophic events (i.e.
445 events referring to 5% of the distributions) should occur (ETL). The absolute and relative values of
446 the ETL was analyzed, as well as the average GM in the 5% of the left-side tail of the function (i.e.
447 the average outcome from the conditions referring to 5% of such cases). The ETL% results suggested
448 that the most limited impact of such events is found in Campania, followed by Sicily with joint place
449 being held by Lazio and Piedmont.

450 In cases of the aforementioned negative events, farmers in Campania could still obtain an outcome
451 ($E[GM]^{95\%}$), which is definitely higher than in other regions. Under these circumstances, farmers in
452 Campania would be expected to lose 70% of their expected GM whilst still obtaining an average of
453 €1,709/ha. Significantly more negative results would occur in the other regions: given such
454 circumstances, farmers would be expected to forgo more than the 90% of their $E[GM]$ and to gain
455 not more than €255/ha (Sicily) and even less in Piedmont (€63/ha). All these results suggested that
456 hazelnut production, especially in Piedmont and Lazio, is affected by high risks and that, under very
457 negative (even if not probable) conditions, the economic results could drop markedly below the level
458 of expected GM. These results also suggested that the four Italian regions differ not only in terms of
459 expected profitability but also in terms of the risk of their activity. And regarding some of these
460 regions, the degree of risk is such that it could well affect the behaviour and well-being of risk-averse
461 farmers.

462

463 *3.3. Factors affecting the risk of the activity – Sensitivity analysis*

464 The results of the sensitivity analysis have been used to quantifying the relative importance of yield,
465 quality and price in generating the overall risk of hazelnut production in four Italian regions. As
466 previously explained, these results are shown by means of tornado graphs, one for each region (Fig.
467 6).

469 Fig. 6. Tornado graphs showing the results of the Regression-Mapped value analysis.
 470 Source: Authors' elaborations on Italian FADN data.
 471

472 Yield is the factor generating the greatest GM variability at the farm level in all regions. The second
 473 factor is product quality, while market price has a minimal effect on GM variability. These results
 474 suggested that farmers should focus their attention more on yield variability than on the other two
 475 factors and, consequently, look for efficient tools to cope with this yield risk. The lack of importance
 476 shown by the prices in the sensitivity analysis is probably linked to the use of annual average data
 477 which tends to reduce intra-annual variability. Evidently, there are differences among regions. Yields
 478 are of greater importance in Campania and Sicily than in the other two regions.

479 Product quality also plays an important role in determining the extent of the risk, especially in
 480 Piedmont. Finally, the price has a very limited role in determining the GM variability in Piedmont
 481 and, even more so, in Sicily. These results highlighted that the regions under consideration also differ
 482 in terms of the sources of risk (i.e. the relative importance of the three considered factors). Hence,
 483 farmers in the four regions may wish to make use of different risk management strategies and tools.
 484 For example, it does not seem useful to have production contracts at pre-determined price levels
 485 whilst it would seem provident to deal with production risk by, for example, underwriting production

486 insurance. While crop yield is the key parameter in stabilizing GM, it also seems important to consider
487 how to manage fluctuations in product quality.

488

489 **4. Discussion and Conclusion**

490 This study has performed a comparative analysis of the profitability and risk profile of hazelnut
491 production, upon which farmers in the four Italian regions rely heavily. This analysis seems timely,
492 given the growing interest in this crop, which is expanding in terms of area under cultivation. This
493 expansion is further assisted by the high price levels observed for the period 2014-2016. The predicted
494 increases in prices and yields, although very gradual, are expected to have a positive impact on the
495 profitability of the crop in the future. An additional factor, which will probably play an important role
496 in crop profitability, regards the quality of the product as the confectionery industry demands high
497 quality hazelnuts (Cristofori et al., 2008). Finally, given the perennial nature of the hazelnut crop, its
498 high establishment costs and a production variability in quality and prices, it is important to pay great
499 attention to risk management and the individual components affecting it, that is, price, yield and
500 product quality.

501 This analysis has permitted the attaining of specific research objectives: (i) to assess the extent of
502 profitability and risk in the four production areas; (ii) to test whether these two factors differ among
503 regions; (iii) to identify the key parameters making the largest contribution to farming-related risk;
504 (iv) and to verify whether there are differences in risk-producing parameters between the four regions.
505 The study areas under investigation differ from each other in several aspects. Campania and Lazio
506 have the most profitable hazelnut production on average while Sicily is the least profitable. Unlike
507 the central-northern regions (where hazelnut production has been adapted to modern and intensive
508 management techniques), Sicily suffers from steep-sloped and small fields which make hazelnut
509 cultivation difficult to mechanise. Moreover, the gross margin risk in Sicily is relatively high, thereby
510 suggesting the requirement to skilfully manage it. This factor differs among the four regions discussed
511 in this research: cultivation in Campania is less risky than in Sicily, Piedmont and Lazio.

512 The sensitivity analysis has provided clear indications that the most important source of risk for all
513 four regions is yield, followed by product quality and, to a lesser extent, market price for hazelnuts
514 without shell. While this is the general pattern in all four areas, the relative magnitude of these sources
515 of risk differs: for example, product quality in Piedmont plays a not indifferent role in determining
516 the overall risk of this crop.

517 The results of this study are in line with those obtained for Italy by the European Commission (2007).
518 Comparing the GM of nut production throughout the EU member states, the Italian GM was found
519 to be the most profitable, followed by the production from Greece, France, Spain and Portugal
520 (European Commission, 2007).

521 Despite the importance of the instability of farm economic results, there is currently a lack of up-to-
522 date empirical evidence regarding this topic. However, various analyses relating to farms specialized
523 in permanent crops are available in the literature. For example, the European Commission (2009) has
524 assessed the extent of EU farms facing a degree of income instability: it was observed that farms
525 specialized in permanent crops (other than vines for wine-making) face a higher income risk than
526 dairy farms and specialized field crop farms. Comparing different farm types for the period 1980-
527 2007, Trestini et al. 2017, confirmed that the farms with a higher probability of a severe income
528 reduction were those specialized in horticulture, permanent crops (other than viticulture) and
529 livestock, with the exception of dairy farms. Severini et al. (2016) also noted that farms specialized
530 in permanent crops face an intermediate level of economic risk (Severini et al., 2016). There are very
531 few analyses relating to single crops: El Benni and Finger (2014) have investigated the riskiness of
532 various Swiss crops, observing that canola and potato produce greater variable net revenues than other
533 crops (such as sugar beet) and, even more so, wheat and barley. Alexander and Moran (2013) have
534 analysed the decision to invest in perennial energy crops and they established that taking into account
535 the variability of crop income affects risk-averse farmers in crop selection. These results could assist
536 farmers in the decision-making of whether to intensify their risk management strategies and which
537 tool to use.

538 The findings outlined in this paper suggest that hazelnut farmers should focus their attention on tools
539 which enable them reduce production risk. The latter include, for example, production insurance
540 which can be used to mitigate the effects of adverse climatic conditions. Less attention should be paid
541 to managing market risk because price volatility has been found as the least important factor affecting
542 the economic performance of hazelnut production. Hence, this suggests that there may be limited
543 interest in developing new tools, such as supply chain contracts, which ensure farmers with constant
544 price levels in this specific sector. Finally, the results outlined in this paper also suggest that there is
545 scope for developing risk management tools to improve farmers' capacity to cope with risks related
546 to the quality of their product. Thus, it could be of benefit to farmers to explore the opportunities
547 offered by more comprehensive risk management instruments such as the Income Stabilization Tool,
548 which is currently supported by the CAP.

549 Two additional points are worth mentioning. First, while the empirical analysis provides different
550 quantitative indicators, the graphical presentation of the results (by means of the PDFs and tornado
551 graphs) also seem useful in communicating results to stakeholders. This is perceived as important
552 because these stakeholders have to decide in accordance with their subjective preferences and local
553 conditions. If additional information regarding the relative preferences of the farmers in the four
554 regions was currently available, it would be possible to extend the analysis by using approaches such
555 as the stochastic efficiency with respect to a function (Hardaker et al., 2004). Unfortunately, no data
556 is currently available to guide the analysis in choosing the form of utility function and the degree of
557 risk aversion of the agents, as required by similar approaches⁶. Second, the results regarding the
558 expected profitability and risk of the activity could be important to agents who are interested in
559 investing in this sector by expanding hazelnut cultivation. Such information could greatly assist
560 investment analyses by developing, for example, net present value analyses accounting for the
561 uncertain nature of economic results, or analyses which account for the dynamic nature of investment

⁶ Given that farmers can be expected to have different risk preferences (see e.g. Iyer et al., 2019), it seems inappropriate to apply the same level of risk aversion to all farmers.

562 decisions, such as those described in Lien et al. (2007). No doubt, further research will pave the way
563 for enhancing the farm risk management of farming systems, those specializing in perennial crops,
564 and thus the resilience and contribution to the local economies of such farms.

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753

754 APPENDIX

755 Table A1

756 Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test results relating to gross margin, yields, quality indicator and prices

Gross margin				
	Piedmont	Lazio	Campania	Sicily
Piedmont	1	-	-	-
Lazio	0.00008376	1	-	-
Campania	2.2e-16	0.8084	1	-
Sicily	0.0001318	0.000002586	0.000003416	1

Yields				
	Piedmont	Lazio	Campania	Sicily
Piedmont	1	-	-	-
Lazio	0.0006961	1	-	-
Campania	0.0001428	0.1186	1	-
Sicily	0.0002387	0.00006432	0.0006702	1

Quality indicator				
	Piedmont	Lazio	Campania	Sicily
Piedmont	1	-	-	-
Lazio	0.0001522	1	-	-
Campania	0.003971	0.1275	1	-
Sicily	0.0003637	0.000000219	0.000005052	1

Price		
	Viterbo CC	Avellino CC
Viterbo CC	1	-
Avellino CC	0.4363	1

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